

Agrisilviculture and Agrosilvopasture

- Agrosilviculture is a type of agroforestry practice that involves the combination of woody perennials either trees or shrubs with crops as understory.
- Silvopasture is mainly supported by the Pillar I CAP in agricultural lands but not by Pillar II.
- Agrosilviculture represents around 1% of the arable lands use in Europe providing a huge potential to be extended.

Defining agrisilviculture

Agrisilviculture is a type of agroforestry practice that involves the combination of woody perennials either trees or shrubs with crops. Agrisilviculture can be implemented in agricultural or forestry lands. In **agricultural lands**, and therefore in areas where CAP Pillar I direct payments can be fully get by farmers agrisilviculture is linked to: (i) **Arable crops**: where crops or mechanically harvested temporary grasslands usually surrounded by hedgerows or spare tree stands to allow crop growth with minimum light interception by the woody perennials (iii) **permanent crops** where different crops such as cereals or dicots are produced as cover crops that can be sold as part of agroecological practices and as a technique for weed management. In **forest lands**, a lack of knowledge on the extent of agrisilviculture happens as no records of forest farming activities are available.

FIGURE 1. Agrosilviculture and Agrosilvopasture cobertura in EU-27. Santiago-Freijanes, J.J.

Silvopasture extent and CAP contribution

Agrisilviculture represents less than 0.01% of the total agricultural agrisilviculture extent in Europe. The CAP agrisilviculture promotion is mostly associating to the promotion of cereals with trees, if the silvoarable practice is considered (Figure 2).

Agrisilviculture promotion by the CAP across Europe

- Agrosilviculture monitoring is needed from croplands to forestlands to make payments associated to agroforestry proved biodiversity, ecosystem services delivery and carbon mitigation promotion as well as forest resilience increase
- Agrosilviculture should be fully paid by Pillar I linked to temporary (mixed with hedgerows) and permanent grasslands (linked to tree linear formation)
- Agrosilviculture should be promoted in Pillar II linked to the establishment and initial maintenance of silvorable practices
- Agrosilviculture promotion should be fostered by cooperation measures recognized at landscape and short value chain level
- Agrosilviculture promotion should be fostered by the CAP considering the type and quality of products it deliver usually linked to multiple value chains considering the global agri-food system and linked to circular economy
- Agrosilviculture promotion should be fostered by the CAP linked to excellent well-trained and independent extension service providers
- Agrosilviculture promotion should be linked to the CAP-Network extension services, knowledge co-creation linked to the promotion of operational groups
- Agrosilviculture should be promoted based on the development of the European

Agroforestry strategy that should include monitoring, promotion, education, advisory, innovation and research at European and National level

MAIN CONCLUSION

- Agrosilviculture integrates woody perennials with croplands that should be promoted by the CAP
- The agrosilviculture promotion is broadly extended as part of the CAP at EU level
- Agrosilviculture should be fostered by the Pillar I and II of the CAP and the promotion should include both the agroecosystem and the agrifood system perspective.

FIGURE 2. Agrisilviculture management with corn, *Populus* and wheat combined in a single plot in Pisa (Tuscany, Italy). Couso, A.

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